

Conclusion

In conclusion, it can be noted that in the case of these semantically related words, in Armenian, Hittite-Iranian languages, it is possible to group identical word pairs with the same meaning. Iranian: *tapasti-* 'fever', *tapasta-* 'carpet' - Armenian: *tapast-* 'fever' and *tapast-* 'carpet, cover', Hittite: *tapaš-* 'fever, heat, disease' and *tapašpa, tapišša, tapašša-* 'a type of cloth or cover'. These parallels in Armenian and Iranian languages give us a possibility not only to find out their parallels of Hittite words existing in other Indo-European languages, which have not been discussed so far, but also to clarify the meaning of the latter.

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STRUCTURAL-SEMANTIC ANALYSIS OF ETHNO-TOPONYMS OF KANGARLI DISTRICT

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Abstract

At present one of the main problems that toponymy face with is the study of ethnonym-based place names spread in different regions of the world. The semantic analysis of such toponyms, as well as the study of the features of their formation is actual in terms of studying the ethnogenesis of nations and the historical ethno-demographic composition of the population in different regions. The article deals with the Kangarli region, located in the northwest of the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic, located near the most ancient centers of civilization in the Middle East and distinguished by its unique features

In order to reveal scientific truths, both toponyms were analyzed in depth, both structurally and semantically, and comparative analyzes and analogies were made between them. A multidisciplinary approach to the issue was put forth for a more in-depth analysis of ethno-toponyms. Such analyzes make it necessary to study ethno-toponyms not only in terms of linguistics, but also in the historical context of ethnogenesis.

Keywords: Azerbaijan, Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic, Kangarli, ethno-toponyms, etymology, structural-semantic analysis.

INTRODUCTION

After Azerbaijan Republic gained freedom and Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic stepped into socio-economic development Kangarli district was established on March 19, 2004 on the basis of a number of settlements which were previously part of Sharur district. Givrag settlement is the administrative center of the district. However, it should be noted that historically, administrative units such as Garabaghlar township, Garabaghlar sultanate, Xok township, Givrag district were existed in the territory of Kangarli district [2].

When analyzing the ethno-oikonims spread in the territory of Kangarli district the first toponym we have to talk about is the name of Kangarli district. In general, being one of the oldest inhabitants of Nakhchivan, governing this land for a long historical period has led to the emergence of numerous ethno-toponyms related to this tribe and its branches in the territory of Nakhchivan, including its north-western region. From this perspective, Kangarli is one of the most interesting and analyzed toponyms and ethnonyms for researchers.

Undoubtedly, the horonym of Kangarli district is also related to the names of Kangarli tribes, and historical, historical-geographical and ethno-demographic factors were taken into account when deciding on such naming of the district. The district was established in 2004.

I. The etymology of Kangarli ethno-toponym

It should be noted that in F. Rashiddaddin's "Oghuzname" [18, p. 13], in the work of Abulgazi Bahadir khan "Shecereyi Tarakime" [22, p. 30] the ethnonym kangarli was mentioned. In both sources, the ethnonym kangarli is explained in the sense of "those with carts, those who have carts".

While explaining the ethnonym, E.Seyidbeyli divided it into three components in the form of "kang-ar-as". He correlated the component "Kang" with the toponym of the river Kang, and showed that the component "ar" means "man", "male". The "as" component was explained as a plural suffix, thus the ethnonym means "men of the Kang River" [21, p. 32-58].

While carrying out lexical-semantic analysis of Kangar, Kengeres and Kangli ethnonyms, A.Gasimov identified the kang // keng component in the word with kun // xun / hun and wrote that it means sun [1]. F.Rzayev explained the word Kangarli in the sense of "old men" and "chief men" [19, p. 161].

II. Place and research directions of ethno-toponyms of Kangarli district in historical sources

The names of ethno-toponyms spread in the territory of modern Kangarli district can be found in various historical sources. At the same time, there are such toponyms that have historically been part of various administrative units in this territory, and today they have passed into a passive background and are almost forgotten.

As early as the 5th century, the Christian author Parbli Lazar spoke of the Kangarlis living in Nakhchivan, South Azerbaijan and surrounding areas, he mentioned the area where they lived as "the country

of the Kangarlis" and the mountain in that area as "Kangarli Mountain" [8, p. 65].

The famous Turkish traveler Evliya Chalabi, who lived in the 17th century, mentioned the city of Garabaghlar in his "Book of Travels".

The "Review Book of Iravan Province" also contains a number of ethno-oikonims that were existed and still exist in the territory of the present-day Kangarli district. It is known from the book that Garabaghlar region that existed at that time have included 8 villages in the territory of today's Kangarli district [11, p.71]. The name of Garabaghlar ethno-toponym was also mentioned in the Review Book as one of the ethno-toponyms that existed in the territory of Kangarli district.

The Russian author of 19th century V.Grigoirev listed the names of present-day Kangarli tribes in his work "Statistical description of Nakhchivan province", many of which are identical with the ethno-oikonims that exist in the Kangarli district today. Among these names mentioned in V.Grigoirev's work, such names as Yurtchu-Girdasar, Garabaghlar should be specially noted [26, p. 32].

I.Chopin also mentioned names of some ethno-oikonims, which are located in the territory of Kangarli district, in his work and one of them is Yurtchu-Girdasar [28, p. 208].

The 19th century Russian author K.N.Smirnov's work "Materials on the history and ethnography of the Nakhchivan land", which is considered a report, mentioned the names of Garabaghlar, Yurtchu toponyms, which are undoubtedly ethno-names, and Xok, Givrag, Shahtakhti toponyms that are described by a number of researchers as ethno-oikonims and settlements are mentioned as villages inhabited by the Kangarlis [27, p. 31].

III. Structural-semantic analysis of ethno-toponyms of Kangarli district

Garabaghlar is one of the most common ethno-oikonim in historical sources. It should be noted that toponyms that are identical and similar to these ethno-oikonims were also registered in Goychay, Khanlar, Agsu, Salyan, Fizuli, Masalli, Khachmaz and Tovuz. Historically, there was a village called Garabaghlar in the territory of Western Azerbaijan (Republic of Armenia). The same place names have been registered in Turkmenistan, Afghanistan, the North Caucasus and Turkey. There are various opinions among the people about the explanation of the toponym of Garabaghlar. The meaning of this word is explained in folk etymology in the forms of "a place with large and numerous gardens", "those who tie a black shoelace to their shoes" and other forms.

Researcher A.Akhundov, while analyzing the structure of the word and giving its meaning, preferred the considerations of "a place with many gardens" and "black garden" [6, p. 47]. M.Seyidov explained the place names "Garabagh" by dividing them into two components "black" and "garden" and wrote that it means "head of the great clan" [20, p. 36]. I.Jafarsoylu correlated the word Garabagh with the "karabek" tribe of Turkic-speaking pecheneg tribes living in the steppes of Eastern Europe in the Middle Ages. In Ajdar

Farzali's researches, the explanation of Garabagh and Garabaghlar toponyms as ethnonyms and anthroponyms was completely denied, the explanation was preferred as a theonym and explained in the sense of "great sacred garden" [5]. In the encyclopedic dictionary "Toponyms of Azerbaijan" the toponym was explained in connection with the name of the Garabaghlar tribe, a branch of the Kangar-Pechenegs [3, p. 125].

A. Bagirov carried out the structural-semantic analysis of the Karabakh toponym and wrote that it was formed from the combination of black, garden parts and plural suffix -s, meaning "big, mighty, strong part" and used to denote a large part of Kangarli [8, p. 73].

We can attribute the Karabakh ethno-oikonim to the group of astonyms, given the size of this settlement and the fact that it has functioned as a city and urban-type settlement in many periods of history.

XIX century Russian authors V. Grigoriev and I. Chopin registered this ethno-oikonim as Yurdchu-Girdasar [26, p. 208]. Mentioning the meaning of the toponym Yurdchu, R. Aliyeva writes that the word "yurd/yurt" means "house, hearth, nest" in Turkish languages [10, p. 74]. Budagov and G. Geybullayev considered this toponym ethno-oikonim and connected it with the name of Yurtchu branch of Poladli tribe of Shahsevens. And as an ethnonym, they explained "Yurtchu" in the sense of art and profession [9, p. 114]. A. Bagirov also described Yurtchu as an ethno-oikonim, but connected this ethno-oikonim with the name of the tribe of Kangarlis of the same name [8, p. 73]. He has written that this tribe lived in the villages of Jahri and Uzunoba, later gathered together and founded the village of the same name in the present-day Kangarli district.

Historian E. Kalbizadeh showed that the toponym Yurdchu was formed in connection with the occupation period of Nakhchivan by the Mongols [12, p. 52].

One of the ethno-oikonims that appeared in the north-western region of the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic in the late twentieth century is the toponym New Karki. It is known that after the occupation of Karki village of Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic by Armenian armed forces in the 90s of the XX century, New Karki village was established for the population who moved from the village. The name of Karki village is formed in connection with the name of Karki tribe. Sources indicate that the Karkis came to Azerbaijan in the early Middle Ages as part of the Kipchaks. At the beginning of the 19th century, it is reported that there is a branch called Kerkibashli within the Kazakhli tribe. A branch of the Turkmens' Ersari tribe was also called Karki. The Karki tribes were also registered in Turkey and Uzbekistan. There are a city, district, settlement called Karki and a mountain called Karkidagh in the territory of Turkmenistan [4, p. 278].

The probability that the Qabilli ethno-oikonim originated with the name of the Qabilli branch of the Kangarli tribe has been suggested by various researchers [8, p. 155].

Khok oikonim is also considered ethno-oikonim by a number of authors. Thus, researchers who show that the name of this place is associated with the Gogar

and Gargar tribes, believe that the initial spelling of the name was Gog. Later, the phonetic substitution of k = x took place [15, p. 456] and the word became Khok.

IV. Analysis of ethno-urbanonyms located in the territory of Garabaghlar village

Urbanonym *Beydili neighborhood* is also an ethno-oikonim. The name of this neighborhood is formed in connection with the name of Beydili tribes.

One of the urbanonyms registered in the territory of Garabaghlar village, which is undoubtedly an ethno-toponym, is the ethno-urbanonym Kurds neighborhood.

One of the most interesting ethno-oikonims – godonyms in the territory of Kangarli district is the name of Garagoyunlu neighborhood in Gabilli village. According to our research and oral surveys carried out in the village, the families living in the neighborhood moved from the south of the Araz River, from the village of Garagoyunlu in present-day Iran. Another ethno-godonym is Gajaris again in Gabilli village.

One of the important places in the system of names of Kangarli district is occupied by station names. It is interesting that some ethnonyms that do not live in the names of villages and settlements are reflected in the names of stations. 4 out of 18 railway stations in the territory of Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic (Bashbashi, Gargalig, Shahtakhti and Givrag stations) are located in Kangarli district, the first two names of which are more interesting for our subject.

V. Structural-semantic analysis of ethno-oronyms of Kangarli district

Among the ethno-oronyms in the territory of Kangarli district, the toponym of Kangarli plain has a special place. It should be noted that even before the establishment of the district as an administrative unit, this area was known among the people as the Kangarli plain.

In addition to the Kangarli plain, another toponym that has an ethno-oronym character in this region is Boyukduz or Bekduz. S. Babayev considered Boyukduz an anthroponym with the name of Bekduz Aman mentioned in the epos "Kitabi Dada Gorgud", and suggested that the name of the Bekduz tribe - ethnonym - was taken from the name of such a tribal leader [7, p. 90-91]. However, we believe that, on the contrary, the Oghuz hero named Aman in the epos was named as Aman from the Bekduzs because he was from the Bekduz tribe. In Mahmud Kashgari's "Divani-lugat-it-Turk", Bugduz is mentioned as one of the 22 Oghuz tribes [24, p. 56]. Most researchers agree that Boyukduz is a transformed version of Bekduz [7, p. 91].

As for the lexical-semantic analysis of the word, it should be noted that in F. Rashiddaddin's "Oghuzname" it is shown that Bukduz, which is a tribe of Uchokhs, means "gentle, mild-mannered, kind" [18, p. 67].

Ottoman Plain Height - At first glance, the Ottoman Plain Height, which looks like an anthroponymic toponym, is located in the eastern part of the Boyukduz [7, p. 92]. Although S. Babayev connects the Ottoman plain with the Ottoman dynasty of kayis, it is impossible to accept it as a convincing version. In our opinion, the initial form of this toponym

was in the form of Asman (As + m + an) and the toponym means "belonging to Ases".

The ethno-oronym yurd Billicy, registered in the territory of Garabaghlar village, was formed in connection with the name of one of the Kangarli tribes. The oronym consists of two components: "Billici" and "yurd". It should be noted that the Billici or Bilici tribe was one of the most influential tribes in the Kangarli tribal union. Researcher M.Guliyev has written that both khan and bey Kangarli cavalries of Nakhchivan belonged to Bilici branch of Kangarli tribe [14]. And "yurd" is a geographical nomen and means "land". Thus, the oronym means "the land belonging to the bilici tribe." It is possible that during the period when Garabaghlar had the status of a sultanate, this area was a separate land where the Bilicis lived, and later it remained in the memory of the people as an oronym.

The toponym of Gazlar gorge in the territory of Garabaghlar village is an ethno-oronym related to guzs / Oghuzs.

Although the area of Beydili spring is an oronym based on a hydronym, it has an ethnonymic character. Beydilis is the name of a tribe that once settled in the territory of Garabaghlar.

The oronym of Sharilgol kovshan has undergone a more complicated development. Thus, first of all, an oikonim-based hydronym Sharilgol appeared on the basis of the word Sharur / Sharil, which has no doubt that it is an ethno-oikonim. Later, on the basis of this hydronym, a new oronym appeared with the participation of the word kovshan.

VI. Structural-semantic analysis of ethno-hydronyms of Kangarli district

Kangarli ethno-hydronyms are also among the names that have been little studied and have not been comprehensively analyzed. The district on the bank of the Araz River is not well supplied with water resources. The density of the river network is weak. The names of a number of natural and artificial lakes and ponds have been registered in the territory of Kangarli district. Among them Ulu Lake, Ghosha Lakes, Ag Lake, Lake Salman, Boyukgol, Lake Zargana, Lake Goyala, Lake Tat, Uch Goze Lake, Lake Gochaga, Lake Mammadali, Lake Haji Huseyngulu, Lake Haji Bakshali, Ghara Lake, Lake Shivil, Lake Bosta, Lake Abdin (Garabaghlar), Lake Sharur (Shahtakhti) can be named. Two of these lakes attract attention as ethno-hydronyms. One of them is Lake Tat and the other is Lake Sharur.

Lake Tat is also one of the rare ethno-hydronyms registered in the Kangarli district in connection with the names of non-Turkic-speaking tribes. It is possible that this ethno-hydronym was formed in connection with the names of Tat workers who came to Nakhchivan from Iran to work in the summer. If we agree with Bahaddin Ogal, we can note that Tat was a single name used to refer to the people living in the Turkic lands, but speaking Persian [23, p. 3].

Most of the springs registered in the territory of Kangarli district, including mineral springs (Baydilbulagi, Asnichay spring, Garabaghlar, etc.) are of ethno-hydronymic nature.

One of the interesting ethno-hydronyms is Beydili spring ethno-hydronym. It should be noted that this ethno-hydronym was registered in the territory of Garabaghlar village of the district and is connected with the name of Beydili, one of the 22 tribes of Oghuzs. This name was first encountered in M.Kashgarli's "Divani-lugat-it-turk" [25, p. 56]. I.Chopin wrote that the Beydilis were also a branch of the Kangarli tribes [28, p. 477].

It should be noted that both the name of the neighborhood and the name of the tribe are registered in the territory of Garabaghlar village in connection with the Beydili tribe. A number of authors write that the Beydilis first settled in Galajik, located near the territory of Garabaghlar, and later moved to the territory of the village [13].

Toponymist Adil Bagirov writes about the meaning of Beydili ethno-oikonim, which took a passive form in the territory of Sharur district: "It can be said without hesitation that Beydili is one of the Oghuz tribes, and in the lexical sense it is used in the sense of "one who cherishes the groom", "dear as adults" and keeps the name of the ancient Turkic tribe alive to this day" [8, p. 78].

Three hydronyms have been identified under the name Asni in the territory of Kangarli district: Asnichay, Asni spring and kahriz Asni. The Asnichay hydronym is associated with the names of the As tribes. When analyzing the toponym from the structural-semantic point of view, it is possible to distinguish three parts: As + ni + chay. As mentioned above, As is associated with the names of the As Turks, who were widespread in the Arazchayi coastal areas of Nakhchivan in the centuries before Christ and chay (river) nomen has been added to the end of the word.

The names of kahrizs also play an important role in the ethno-hydronyms system of the district. In the past, 169 kahriz were recorded only in the Kangarli inclined plain and about 60 in the Boyukduz inclined plain [17, p. 253]. Kahriz names such as Asni, kahriz Tat, Agh su, which currently exist in the district, are ethno-hydronym.

Kahriz Agsu is located in the territory of Yurdchu village of Kangarli district. Another name for Kahriz is "Boyuk Chay". Studies show that the Agsu hydronym is not a descriptive toponym. From the structural-semantic point of view, the toponym consists of two components: ag (white) + su (water) components. We see the "white" component in the names of many medieval Turkic tribes, including the White Huns, the White Sakas, the White Caspians, and others. The "water" component is associated with the names of Su (water) Turkic tribes. It can be assumed that the second component was formerly in the form of "sak", and later, as a result of phonetic changes, Agsak became Agsu.

The ethno-hydronym of kahriz Tat was registered in Garabaghlar village of the district. As mentioned above in the explanation of the hydronym of Lake Tat, this toponym was also formed in connection with the names of Iranian-speaking groups who came to the region to work seasonally.

Conclusion

The lexical structure of toponyms of Kangarli district consists of Turkic names. As a result, we believe that the origin of toponyms here was created in connection with this country, this land, the life experience, way of thinking, traditions of our ancestors and the names of various tribes and tribal associations involved in the formation history of our people.

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